

COMPARATIVE EDUCATION: PEDAGOGY IN BUSINESS ORGANIZATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the theme related to the application of pedagogical precepts to the business environment, which became known as Business Pedagogy. This is a subject of intense social relevance, because the business world needs pedagogical support in the field of training, preparation and investment in productivity. It is a bibliographical, exploratory investigation, based on renowned authors in the study of business behavior. In the business environment, Pedagogy will aim to establish relationship parameters, in which everyone respects each other within the value standards of human dignity, seeking to prevent the emergence of ideologies in which the ends justify the means; however, it will not act as a tool capable of emasculating individuals in their deepest ambitions and desires. In the exercise of its praxis, within organizations, it can also practice training and professional education programs supporting changes and enabling better results with a better quality of life; use techniques in order for professionals to recognize themselves in the process of change that is being inserted; select seminars and workshops for all company professionals from management to employees; employ unique projects, with fixed goals without waste, with low costs, on time with qualitative and quantitative parameters; defines the integration of the two levels; make entrepreneurs aware

of the existing problems, and thus improve the self-esteem of employees; report their coupling, promoting the right balance between technical competence and social competence, making them more active and motivated. The difference in the performance of the pedagogue in the company, among the different organizational departments, is that this professional has as main assumption: the formation of the group; didactics; the philosophical structure; the humanistic condition; the human resources policy adopted by the organization. What can be concluded is that Pedagogy is the result of a praxis, understanding this as the relationship of reciprocity and simultaneity between theory and practice, that is, before becoming science, synthesis, it is practical action, study, observation, analysis, interpretation, conflict resolution and Business Pedagogy is all the above applied to business organizations, aiming at building a pedagogical environment, to understand this expression, an environment that learns and also teaches.

Keywords: Business Pedagogy; Pedagogues; Pedagogical training; Comparative education.

INTRODUCTION

In this article we will start from the definition of Pedagogy as a science that takes care, directly, of the technical training of professionals who will work in scientific processes, aimed at learning and teaching, aiming at adapting human beings to their environment, in a way that allows them to act pragmatically about it. This may seem like a pleonasm, because a mechanism that appears to be profound, in itself, can already be understood as a procedure that integrates experience and theory in its activities.

Pedagogy can be interpreted as a science that becomes necessary wherever there are human beings, because there are processes of intra- and interpersonal relationships occurring naturally; resulting from *simple and/or complex conflicts*, in the same proportion as it produces them.

When introducing it and its portfolio in companies, the fact is that other sciences and pseudosciences have already failed to reach the level of excellence expected in this field. However, to meet an environment so marked by the demand for quality in the services provided and products developed by high competitiveness, both internally and externally, there would be a need to adapt and create specific knowledge to the company that school pedagogy has, adapting it to the business world.

The company is no longer a place where only equipment is produced and exchanges of goods for equivalent values, to expand towards the customer, where they seek satisfaction, not only with the product and service they acquire as also in service. And this change in consumer behavior has forced companies to reformulate their internal mechanisms, seeking to create an environment in which their employees remain attentive to coexistence with each other, so that this harmony is reflected in direct customer service.

It is from this thinking that Business Pedagogy is developed, an offshoot of classic pedagogical thinking, without however having the opportunity to be applied to procedures for developing the human structure within business organizations; with the aim of improving processes, in which deeper and more dynamic problems are involved than those experienced in traditional schools. Furthermore, Business Pedagogy wishes to create an environment, which can offer conditions for the development of conditions, whose values and behaviors are often in opposition to what Academy teachers, as a rule, try to modify and/or destroy in their students, the highlight the feeling of competitiveness and individuality.

Feelings such as ambition, dispute, competition, the desire to overcome the opponent, *even the view of the other as an opponent to be defeated at any cost*, are abhorred themes in schools that no longer train men; because our educational system is full of figures deluded with the idea of equality and harmony without increasing individual and social wealth; consequently, respect is not established between such figures, since they all believe they are equal in all areas of social existence.

In the business environment, Pedagogy will aim to achieve the establishment of relationship parameters, in which everyone respects each other within the standards of value of human dignity, seeking to prevent the emergence of ideologies in which the ends justify the means; however, it will not act as a tool capable of emasculating individuals in their deepest ambitions and desires.

The pedagogue, as a requirement for the effective exercise of his praxis, requires general knowledge and skills of knowing how to think, knowing how to listen, learning to learn, dealing with authority, dealing with contemporary technologies, having initiative to solve problems, having the ability to make decisions, be creative, be autonomous, be in tune with contemporary reality and have social responsibility, combined with knowing how to do, knowing how to innovate, knowing how to create, knowing how to transform, considering that companies need practical men.

This is the inclusive basis for the pedagogue to contribute to the task of democratizing access, by the greatest number of individuals, to the knowledge produced by science, aiming, among other objectives, at promoting improvements in the conditions of social life, integrated into the processes of business management, understanding the internal and external relationships that interfere in the complex and [*not at all harmonious coexistence between*] man, company and productivity.

Conflict is something inherent to human beings and their existence in society. It appears at the exact moment when one wants one thing and is forced to do another, opposing interests

; or when you find yourself hampered by the interests of others. When life and the existential condition are questioned, this is the greatest conflict that haunts human thought, and it is in this space of misunderstanding of being in the world that opportunists weave their webs, creating clashes within business organizations, transforming them into objects of love and hate from the professionals who work there.

Considering that the pedagogue is a necessary professional, *and not just useful*, in all instances in which there is simultaneity between learning and teaching, which means the existence of broad fields of pedagogical activity, in the different areas of knowledge acquired. It is up to him to apply in the establishment of integration between all the company's organizational groups, together with the workers, using, for this purpose, a pedagogical management where a data collection would be carried out, which would make the company aware of the existing problems that, through dynamics would have the didactic performance of all employees. After the result, we move on to implementing methodological projects that enable the training of individuals and the consequent increase in productivity, both at a personal and organizational level.

What must be very clear is the idea that it is the existence of conflict that allows growth, both for individuals and organizations. When trying to solve them, the capabilities and potential of each component of the process (people and company) are revealed and it is in this interstice that the figure of the Pedagogue proves to be relevant to the point of justifying investments in his work within the company .

In exercising your practice, within organizations, you can also practice training and professional development programs, sustaining changes and enabling better results with a better quality of life; use techniques so that professionals recognize themselves in the change process that is being inserted; select seminars and *workshops* for all company professionals, from management to employees; employ unique projects, with goals set without waste, with low costs, within the deadline with qualitative and quantitative parameters; define the integration of the two levels; make businesspeople aware of existing problems, and thus improve employees' self-esteem ; relate the coupling of these, promoting the fair balance between technical competence and social competence, making them more active and motivated.

The difference in the pedagogue's role in the company, between the different organizational departments, is that this professional's main assumption is: the formation of the group; didactics; the philosophical structure; the humanistic condition; the human resources policy adopted by the organization. With a different perspective, its purpose is to promote changes in the behavior of individuals so that they improve both the quality of their professional

and personal performance, considering that the pedagogue is concerned with the training and development of human beings from an integral perspective, where he does not see the employee as a machine that cannot make mistakes.

According to Chiavenato (1999), when carrying out training, some factors are considered such as the cooperation of the company's managers and coordinators, the quality and preparation of the instructors and the profile of the apprentices. Thus, the expectation is that training will result in a logical and pragmatic response to extremely changeable environmental conditions and new requirements for survival and organizational growth.

Within an organization, regardless of the size and marketing field in which it has specialized, what moves a given company are individuals and, in addition, it is their feelings and expectations that make it act more competitively. in the market. And, wherever there are people, there are conflicts [*of all kinds*] and it is not about eliminating them, putting an end to them, which is already impossible , nor controlling them , which is a utopian, puerile idea, for be more exact; therefore, these different conflicting feelings, in themselves, represent opportunities for development and gains for the institution and are not necessarily the root cause of the ruin of many of them.

The pedagogue, in this privileged space of conflicts and interests, can contribute so that each of those involved can develop action strategies that boost the company's growth and, along with it, also theirs, which results in strengthening the group. It is a complex process, which becomes more difficult to understand due to our academic training, which is still based on archaic models , according to which everyone within an organizational space has to be friends and well connected. The agenda must be the issue of respect for the inalienable rights of each person; However, challenges and ego disputes are healthy and must persist, because human beings are, by nature, competitive.

HISTORICAL CONTEXT OF PEDAGOGY

Interestingly, Pedagogy has existed since Classical Antiquity, with the variant that in its beginnings, it was the expression of the pedagogue's praxis; The action of this individual, who was a servant, responsible for taking the aristocratic child to school and then for managing his independent study processes resulted in a procedure, which was called pedagogy.

Thus, the pedagogue appears before Pedagogy and, for the sake of clarification, this individual was not a slave, as is considered in contemporary thought. It was family property, therefore it had a master, a citizen, who was its rightful owner.

This servant had the responsibility of taking care of the safety of the aristocrats' children, taking them safely to their place of study and then ensuring that the tasks determined by the mentor were carried out to the letter, and could even punish the child if he did not fulfilled what was determined by the master: in this sense, the child's education was his responsibility.

With Roman rule, pedagogues began to create specific teaching and learning methods, since, in Rome, they literally became teachers, representing the first step towards Pedagogy becoming a science with its methods, principles, epistemological categories, precepts and definitions of man, the world, knowledge, and, much later, had its own chair at universities. With this, it became a field of theoretical studies, combined with practical activities that seek to align scientific thinking with the transmission of pragmatic content, aiming at the integral formation of man.

In Brazil, the Pedagogy course was created in 1939, through Decree-Law no. 1,190, when the National Faculty of Philosophy of the University of Brazil was organized. Since its origins, it has been oriented towards the training of the Pedagogue as a teacher, providing the student with a set of knowledge that guarantees the status of educator and trainer.

As time went by, there were new educational demands and the Pedagogy course began to offer qualifications in School Administration, Educational Guidance and School Supervision and to train teachers to teach the pedagogical subjects of the 2nd ^{year teaching course}. Degree. There were many movements, both by teachers and student groups, in order to define the identity of this professional linked to his area of activity, as well as his field of work.

During the São Paulo State Congress of Pedagogy Students, held in 1967, students demanded action in relation to the field of work of Pedagogy graduates. And these students went much further when they effectively recommended the creation of positions and functions through which qualified professionals – those with degrees in Pedagogy – could meet the educational needs of the Brazilian reality in the following sectors: educational planning, educational TV, programmed instruction, adult education, formulation of a philosophy of education and reformulation of an educational policy, education of exceptional people, specialization in educational levels, development of human resources, community activities, performance evaluation in schools and companies, personnel administration (analysis and classification positions, recruitment, selection, placement and training of personnel).

Given the scope of the requests, the students demanded [*by extension*] the insertion of the Pedagogue also in the company, working on the development of human resources, performance evaluation, personnel administration that involves job analysis, personnel recruitment, having in view of their theoretical and technical training in the educational field.

Students at that time already felt that professionals qualified in Pedagogy were also able to assume these roles and functions in companies.

This need was already evident in the reality of the job market and students were aware of this perception. There was, therefore, a need to increase the training of Pedagogues, via the curriculum. However, the legislation at the time did not take this demand into consideration, meaning that training was destined for courses offered by other institutions, outside the Official Education System. Only recently has some Higher Education institutions been offering the Business Pedagogy modality to interested pedagogues, as a specialization [*latu sensu*].

From the 1990s onwards, Pedagogy courses began to be restructured at Universities, including qualifications for teaching in Early Childhood Education and Special Education. From the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education of 1996, the Pedagogy Course now aims to train teachers capable of analyzing and intervening in the educational reality, guaranteeing solid knowledge of Education Sciences and Pedagogical Sciences, through study of subjects and the Theoretical Foundations of Education.

Thus, the course enables the Pedagogue, as an education professional, to know and recognize pedagogical work in its entirety, aiming to make him an articulator and organizer of the didactic-pedagogical process wherever it occurs, always seeking and aiming to improve quality. teaching and learning of individuals involved in the mission.

Therefore, the Pedagogy course today forms a Pedagogue teacher, capable of combining the capacity for theoretical-didactic reflection and a broad view of education, being able to organize and implement consistent and effective actions that aim to fully guarantee learning.

The National Education Guidelines and Bases Law (Law 9394/1996) allows Universities to organize their respective curricula in order to meet emerging areas of society, offering alternative disciplines and thematic centers, focusing on the need that society has expressed towards the divisions and fragmentations that still occur in the spaces where educational processes take place are eliminated.

The academic world recognizes that educational work must currently occur in a more holistic dimension and in an interdisciplinary way, creating an integrative and comprehensive vision of pedagogical work, with a Pedagogue who has the capacity, skill and competence to develop their autonomy, creativity and commitment to improving internal and external teaching and learning conditions.

BUSINESS PEDAGOGY

Defiantly, the performance of Business Pedagogy , as an instance concerned with creating conditions, which can increase the company's wealth , now present in an environment foreign to its original scope, is to make professionals qualified to work in the field of teaching, able to think strategies for a historical organizational and systems management context, expanding the production of knowledge in various areas of non-school education . This knowledge is scientific and technological, aiming at the integration of human beings into a world that is increasingly integrated from the perspective of developing analytical and synthetic capacity, questioning and developing policies that directly and indirectly address the issues humanities, in addition to bringing the future pedagogue closer to the nature of the role he intends to perform as a technician, capable of carrying out experiments and drawing on them to develop theories and syntheses.

The pedagogue, inserted in business organizations, is responsible for properly analyzing the situations in which conflicts occur and the best way to transform them into gains for greater leaps towards the success of the entire group and the company, in a macro way. When devising the failed strategy of nullifying the points of impact, without each party involved having the proper possibility to reflect on what leads them to such a feeling of confrontation, in a short time, there is an environment in which the relationships between the Individuals gradually lose all their authenticity until they no longer survive.

The human being is a creature that forms groups, according to their convictions and beliefs, interests, conscious and unconscious affinities. Therefore, it is natural that this feeling that it already brings with it as a phylogenetic inheritance is heightened within an environment of high competitiveness, which is the modern company, inserted in a value system such as capitalism. When the human being is deprived of his condition in question, what is left is a strange and lackluster creature, deluded and lost about his own convictions in the space he occupies as protagonist, who knows what?!... In this sense, the business pedagogue can be understood as the person responsible for creating situations of *fair balance* within the coexistence space, leading each party to maintain due respect for the other. Pedagogues, according to the empiricist, are the best suited to establish practices with leaders, aiming at an efficient and effective way of relating to employees , so that tasks can be carried out more productively.

Human existence, in itself, is already marked, in its essence, by complexity, taking into account this word used in this context, as something really far from the possibility of a logical

and plausible explanation. When other intangible elements such as ambition, the desire to overcome, competitiveness and the need for survival are added to this *sui generis condition*, we have a condition in which the already known sciences fail to explain the human being, because of their visions marked by biases characteristic of their respective scopes of investigation and application of thought on the thing given and analyzed.

It wouldn't take much longer than it did for Pedagogy, as an autonomous science, to enter the spaces of business organizations, offering its knowledge about human nature, in contact with others and in conflict, too. The view that the role of Pedagogy has to do with the integral formation of man, a precept developed and disseminated in classical Cuban thought, in which a holistic view of this doctrine was developed, has caused companies, entities that work with expectations to at all times, these are implied under the ideas of goals to be achieved.

They discovered that, without adequate *pathological support* for the individuals inserted there for years on end, there was a need to apply techniques that, in addition to being able to explain human behavior in groups, could also find and even develop mechanisms for adjusting the space. -time, since individuals have shown themselves to be increasingly crazy and disconnected from their existential conditions and organizations need their employees to be focused on processes, aiming for excellent, ever-increasing results.

The sociological bias that took over organizations in the 19th century and which showed some efficiency was replaced by a psychologization of life confined in the centers of business activity, which showed some progress until proving that it ignored the human being in its gnosiological and empirical integrality and great projects failed, which opened up space for new perspectives on how to deal with working life.

This is why Pedagogy proves to be the most efficient in dealing with human beings, because it does work that remains outside the intrinsic existential condition of each individual, that is, it does not scare them because it does not invade their privacy; advises without imposing conditions, proposes advances and assists on this journey, showing itself closer to each person's lived reality. With the increasingly advanced technology of industrial production, competition between companies becoming more intense and, finally, the mergers and acquisitions of traditional holding companies, in which the monopoly of previously dominated markets is interrupted, leading to the need to have employees within the production spaces in which they become collaborators, that is, individuals who work together with their employers to win and surpass a market that is changing radically and that starts to deal with a more intense, better informed and more daring consumer in their social perspectives. To achieve this, it is not

enough to master conditioning and repression techniques; There is a need to balance and no longer control the feelings of each individual's actions within the company in which they work.

From the 1970s onwards, there was an increasing automation of the work process and the emergence and insertion of new technologies in industrial production processes. However, the working class, as much as the business class, was unprepared for industrial development and was leading the labor market to demand the professionalization of workers to keep up with the changes **that** were occurring as a result of the imminent technological transformations that were occurring in increasingly accelerated mode.

However, educational institutions were unprepared to offer any contributions to the professionalization of workers so that they could meet the prospects of industrial development at the speed with which it was seen happening. Scientific research, in the most diverse production sectors, showed possibilities for advancement in technical production and innovation that contributes to increased production, in the most diverse sectors.

The school aimed to contribute to the acceleration of economic development and social progress, in which the basic principles were technical rationality, worker efficiency and productivity, the principle of economics for education, reconciling with the developmental policy based on principles of the theory of human intellectual capital, present on the national scene, supported by policies and actions aimed at improving the industrial and economic system.

Professional training began to have its area defined based on the demands of the job market and in it, through intensive training, coordinated by institutions or by the company itself. Initially, the pedagogue found a company with Taylorist-Fordist characteristics and with workers with little or no education.

During the decade, 1970, the company's concern was to have on its staff a worker with basic education, but with practical knowledge, because if he only has basic education, his knowledge of the activity carried out was achieved through the simplest possible experience of the activity he was carrying out. would develop and not promote conflicts. The human relations courses were part of the training process that, in most cases, was taught by the pedagogue in partnership with the psychologist.

The pedagogue was responsible for coordinating educational programs, such as those that provided basic education to employees within formal education and training programs, to meet the company's needs. Entrepreneurs during this period wanted workers to have some knowledge of elementary basic education, such as knowing how to read, write and follow scripts. This form of action acted in accordance with the production model with Taylorist-

Fordist characteristics, which centered its training actions on the construction of technical knowledge and know-how. During this period (1970s), due to formal schools not meeting market expectations, professional training took place in the workplace and became of great relevance, providing a variety of training.

Education has undergone changes in its concept, it is no longer restricted to the teaching-learning process in formal school spaces, leaving the school environment and moving towards different and diverse segments.

The Pedagogue was also forced to undergo epistemological transformations regarding his work and its adjustments, aiming to adapt to this new reality, positioning himself as a qualified professional together with the changing society and its demands, seeking to unite knowledge and integration in business management processes, understanding the internal and external relationships that affect the coexistence of man, company and productivity.

They developed participatory and quality management development and implementation programs; human resources administration, such as planning, executing, controlling and evaluating personal and professional development programs; professional selection and guidance; professional and business ethics programs.

The term *Business Pedagogy* was coined by Prof. Maria Luiza Marins Holtz to designate activities to encourage professional and personal development carried out within companies. For Holtz:

Pedagogy and the Company make a perfect marriage. Both have the same objective in relation to people, especially in current times. A Company is always an association of people, to explore an activity with a defined objective, led by the businessman, an enterprising person, who directs and leads the activity in order to achieve also defined ideas and objectives. Pedagogy is the science that studies and applies doctrines and principles aiming at a program of action in relation to the formation, improvement and stimulation of all the faculties of people's personalities, in accordance with defined ideals and objectives (HOLTZ, 1996, p. 46) .

Holtz (1996) expresses, in this epigraph, what Pedagogy and the performance of the Pedagogue are, in fact, expected to be, as a professional in the field of human sciences. By having a broad training, in terms of knowledge of different segments of scientific knowledge, from childhood to adulthood, this allows you to understand, with greater capacity, how events occur or should occur in human lives.

Pedagogical work goes far beyond a synthetic elaboration of an idea to be applied to a specific object and towards a concrete objective; it proposes more than solving a problem, because it first delves into knowing the problem that produces it and in which it is immersed,

which means that the entire result is evaluated as the product of long systematic studies, with proven and recognized scientific validity. .

It is in this sense that the training of the Pedagogue and the recognition of his profession is intended, which, as already highlighted in other parts of this book, is the product of his empirical work and which, once taken to the level of theoretical understanding, becomes a science autonomous and with a diverse and compelling field of action.

All human life is marked by education, regardless of the spaces in which one is immersed and, within business organizations, once again not distinguishing their dimension or field of exploration, the most diverse challenges are posed and the individuals inserted there need educate themselves and be educated, because in man's dealings with nature there are limits that cannot be exceeded under penalty of severe punishment or facing various problems. For the human being, the limit is the other and this other is not, necessarily, another human, an unreasonable idea that has placed the human being in the spotlight of existence and peaceful coexistence with the Environment in which he is inserted as an active and more active being. once, he understands his condition of activity as acting to modify everything around him, seeking to satisfy his own ego as a way of showing his value, especially to himself.

Pedagogy, understood as a science that starts from the empirical to the theoretical [*and not the other way around*], proposes the dialogue between man and himself and takes as its principle the maxim that was recorded in the portico of the Oracle of Delphi: “Man, know yourself. yourself!”, where the oracle [*the revelation*] was already given, there being no need to ask the Pythoness what Destiny had in store for her. “Man’s dialogue with himself” was the way Plato proposed this phrase: an internalization of knowledge and abandonment of the world of experience.

This idea of building and delineating the personological structure goes beyond the limits of school and reaches companies, because the process of influences received by the participants of a Company, throughout the time they work there, is Education.

It is essential that the Business Pedagogue is aware that Education, purely human, however refined it may be, does not fully fulfill man, and this is because man has aspirations of *Infinity* , given that he feels incomplete in the face of life.

A. Maslow goes so far as to say that the human being is a needy creature and every time he satisfies a need, another appears in its place, the result of his desire. It is demonstrated metaphysically and historically that man, everywhere and always, even when he denies the *Infinite* , feels attraction for the *Infinite* and the need for human satisfaction is something, strictly, infinite.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Business Pedagogy has taken on new organizational scenarios, where pedagogues work in the development of human resources, performance evaluation, personnel administration that involves job analysis, personnel recruitment, due to their theoretical and technical training in the educational area, making - be able to reconcile systematic reflection with a broad view of educational and training processes in different spaces of human coexistence, being able to organize and program consistent and effective actions that guarantee professional learning, aiming at an action program in relation to training, improvement and stimulation of all faculties of the individual personality, forming inquiring subjects, capable of proposing questions and not just giving answers, which leads to the construction of a professional capable of investigating, reflecting, generating knowledge, teaching both at school and in non-school spaces.

To this end, both pedagogy and companies act towards the realization of defined ideals and objectives, in the work of bringing about changes in the behavior of people who live inside and outside the school, having the responsibility of knowing the solutions to the issues that involve the productivity of human people, the objective of every company, to know and work towards the particular objectives of the company where you work in order to drive development in the company among managers and employees, towards the defined objectives, human and business. Promoting conditions that lead to human coexistence in this company in the field of extra-school pedagogical action, which is what most interests the objectives of this work, working in pedagogical consultancy or in the human resources sector, acting with ethics and commitment with a view to building a fair society.

What can be concluded is that Pedagogy is the result of praxis, understanding this as the relationship of reciprocity and simultaneity between theory and practice, that is, before becoming science, synthesis, it is practical action, study, observation, analysis, interpretation, conflict resolution.

Business Pedagogy is all of the above applied to business organizations, aiming to build a pedagogical environment, to understand this expression, an environment that learns and also teaches.

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